

ADVANCING THE DIGITIZATION AND ANALYSIS OF DYNAMIC
CULTURAL HERITAGE OBJECTS

KINETIKA D1.6

Project Website and Logo Design

Lead Beneficiary	USAL
Due Date	27/02/2026
Status	Final
Version	3.0
Dissemination level	Public (PU)

Funded by
the European Union

KINETIKA has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Innovation Actions under Grant Agreement No. 101233379 – KINETIKA. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

KINETIKA D1.6

Deliverable information

Work package	WP1
Tasks	T1.1 – Project Management and Coordination v1
Lead Beneficiary	USAL
Main Authors	Diego González-Aguilera (USAL), Natalia Nuño Villanueva (USAL), Pablo Pedreira Soto (USAL), María Blanca Nieto Santos (USAL)
Collaborators	-
Reviewers	Aris Zompras (ACCELI), Andreas Almpanis (IED ES)

Abstract

This deliverable documents the definition and implementation of the visual identity and project website of KINETIKA. It describes the conceptual and technical approach adopted to establish the project's initial public-facing assets, ensuring coherence with the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage ecosystem and compliance with European Commission communication requirements. The document outlines the main design principles, implementation choices, and constraints considered in the development of these assets, which together provide a consistent and sustainable foundation for KINETIKA's communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement activities throughout the project.

VERSION CONTROL

Version	Date	Main author	Description
0.1	20/01/2026	NNV (USAL)	Draft outline
0.2	23/01/2026	MBNS (USAL)	Logo guideline draft
0.3	27/01/2026	PPS (USAL)	Website draft
1.0	06/02/2026	DGA (USAL)	Final version
2.0	18/02/2026	PPS (USAL)	Added reviewer suggestions
3.0	24/02/2026	NNV (USAL)	Final formatting and suggestions

1. CONTENT TABLE

Version control 3

List of figures 5

List of tables 6

Terms and abbreviations 7

Executive summary 8

1. Introduction 9

 1.1. Background 9

 1.2. Purpose and scope 9

 1.3. Approach 10

 1.4. Relation to other Work packages, Tasks and Deliverables 11

 1.5. Document structure 12

2. Visual identity 13

 2.1. Logo Design and overview 13

 2.2. Official logo variations 15

 2.2.1. Layout adaptations 15

 2.2.2. Colour options 16

 2.3. Logo application guidelines 17

 2.3.1. Correct usage principles 17

 2.3.2. Access to Branding documentation 18

3. Project website 19

 3.1. Website structure 19

 3.2. Design and Visual Identity 27

 3.3. Functionality and Features 28

 3.4. Content Management and Updates 29

 3.5. Security, Privacy, and Compliance 29

 3.6. Analytics and Performance Monitoring 30

Bibliography and references 31

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Approach visual workflow..... 10

Figure 2. Relationship map of Deliverable D1.6 within the KINETIKA project..... 11

Figure 3. Conceptual structure of Deliverable D1.6.....12

Figure 4. Official KINETIKA logo – horizontal configuration. 14

Figure 5. KINETIKA logo colour palette. 14

Figure 6: KINETIKA master logo with clear space defined..... 14

Figure 7. KINETIKA logo – vertical configuration. 15

Figure 8. KINETIKA compact logo – horizontal configuration. 15

Figure 9. KINETIKA compact logo – vertical configuration..... 15

Figure 10. KINETIKA logo – horizontal greyscale.16

Figure 11. KINETIKA logo – vertical greyscale.16

Figure 12. KINETIKA compact logo – horizontal greyscale.....16

Figure 13. KINETIKA compact logo – vertical greyscale.....16

Figure 14. KINETIKA logo – horizontal white.....16

Figure 15. KINETIKA logo – vertical white.....16

Figure 16. KINETIKA compact logo – horizontal white.....17

Figure 17. KINETIKA compact logo – vertical white.....17

Figure 18: KINETIKA’s Logo Guidelines. 18

Figure 19. KINETIKA Homepage – Banner view.....21

Figure 20. KINETIKA Homepage – Objectives and News view.21

Figure 21. KINETIKA Homepage – Newsletter and footer view.....22

Figure 22. KINETIKA About>KINETIKA – KINETIKA technologies.22

Figure 23. KINETIKA About>ECCCH.....23

Figure 24: KINETIKA About>Sister Projects.24

Figure 25. KINETIKA Pilot Cases – Overview.....24

Figure 26. KINETIKA Contact.26

Figure 27. ECCCH shared website aesthetics.....27

Figure 28. KINETIKA Funding information.28

Figure 29. KINETIKA ECCCH footer.28

Figure 30. KINETIKA website – tablet.....28

Figure 31. KINETIKA website- mobile phone.....28

Figure 32. KINETIKA website – cookies disclaimer.....30

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. KINETIKA Website structure – Sections and subsections.....20

TERMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CH	Cultural Heritage
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
ECHOES	European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
M	Month
OC	Open Call
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SME	Small and Midsize Enterprise
SMTP	Simple Mail Transfer Protocol
T	Task
USAL	University of Salamanca
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable (D1.6) presents the design and implementation of the KINETIKA project website and visual identity, establishing the first public-facing elements of the project. It serves as a foundation for communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement activities, ensuring that KINETIKA is clearly recognisable and aligned with the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) ecosystem. D1.6 is part of Work Package 1 (WP1), “Project Coordination, Communication, and Dissemination,” and supports the definition of a coherent visual identity, the deployment of the official project website, and the alignment of KINETIKA’s communication tools with the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) and the European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science (ECHOES) guidelines. It provides the first structured interface for presenting project objectives, activities, and outputs to the wider cultural heritage (CH) community.

The main outcomes of this deliverable include (I) the final KINETIKA logo, developed through an iterative process from the proposal-stage version to the version formally approved by the ECHOES coordination team, ensuring recognisability and coherence with the ECCCH visual framework. Building on the logo, (II) the project website, developed on a WordPress platform to ensure flexibility and maintainability, while supporting ongoing content updates and stakeholder engagement.

Overall, D1.6 establishes the visual and digital foundations for KINETIKA’s public presence, providing a robust, maintainable, and fully compliant platform that will support communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement throughout the project lifecycle.

1. INTRODUCTION

This introductory section provides the general framework for understanding the objectives, methodology, and broader context of Deliverable D1.6 within the KINETIKA project[1]. KINETIKA is developed under the framework of the ECCCH, coordinated by the ECHOES project[2]. It aims to establish a robust digital ecosystem for CH institutions, promoting interoperability, stakeholder engagement, and the dissemination of innovative tools and services across Europe[3]. Deliverable D1.6 plays a foundational role in this context by defining KINETIKA's public-facing identity through its logo and project website.

This first section of D1.6 begins by presenting the background and context that underpin the deliverable (1.1), followed by a clear definition of its purpose and scope (1.2). The approach followed to design and implement both the visual identity and website is then described (1.3). The deliverable's relationship with other WPs, tasks (T), and dissemination activities within KINETIKA is clarified to highlight its integrative role in supporting communication and ecosystem engagement (1.4). Finally, the document structure is outlined (1.5) to guide the reader through the sections covering visual identity, website design, content management, and technical implementation.

1.1. BACKGROUND

As mentioned before, KINETIKA is developed within the framework of the ECCCH, under the coordination of the ECHOES project, which establishes a common ecosystem for digital services, tools, and standards supporting CH institutions across Europe. Within this context, clear visibility, coherence, and alignment with ECCCH communication and co-branding requirements are essential from the early stages of the project. From the outset of KINETIKA, the definition of a dedicated visual identity and the deployment of an official project website were identified as key elements to support communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement activities. These assets constitute the primary public-facing interfaces of the project, enabling transparent access to project objectives, activities, and expected outcomes, while ensuring compliance with European Commission (EC) visibility rules[4] and ECCCH guidelines[5].

D1.6 is the first formal deliverable of the KINETIKA project. As such, it establishes the foundations of the project's public presence and does not build upon inputs from specific WPs, Ts, or previous Ds. Instead, it defines the formal and visual baseline that will guide subsequent communication and dissemination actions throughout the project, ensuring consistency in form, structure, and presentation across all future outputs.

1.2. PURPOSE AND SCOPE

The purpose of D1.6 is to define, document and present the official visual identity (in this case the official logo) and project website of KINETIKA, ensuring a coherent, recognisable and compliant communication framework from the early stages of the project (M1). This deliverable aims to establish a solid foundation for all future communication, dissemination and outreach activities, supporting the visibility of KINETIKA while reinforcing its alignment with the ECCCH ecosystem and the ECHOES coordination framework.

The scope of this deliverable covers the showcase of the KINETIKA official logo, the associated visual elements and colour palette, and the conceptual and technical implementation of the project website. It describes the adopted approach, design rationale, structural organisation and technical choices made to deliver a functional, accessible and easily maintainable online presence. The website is conceived as a public dissemination tool, providing general information about the project objectives, activities and consortium and results.

This deliverable is primarily addressed to the EC, project partners, and relevant stakeholders involved in CH research and innovation, serving both as a formal project output and as a reference document for consistent use of KINETIKA's visual and digital assets. The content is limited to the initial definition and implementation of the logo and website; ongoing content updates, dissemination actions and future enhancements fall outside the scope of this document and will be addressed within the corresponding WPs throughout the project duration.

1.3. APPROACH

The preparation of D1.6 followed a structured and pragmatic approach combining design definition and technical implementation. The methodology was oriented towards delivering a functional and easily maintainable project website together with a highly recognisable visual identity that clearly distinguishes KINETIKA while reinforcing its belonging to the ECCCH ecosystem. The process (Figure 1) started with the development of the KINETIKA logo. An iterative design process was carried out, evolving from the initial version submitted to the EC at proposal stage[1] to the final version formally presented in this deliverable. This process included internal refinement and validation by the ECHOES coordination team to ensure full alignment with the established guidelines, allowing KINETIKA to remain visually distinctive while being immediately identifiable as part of the ECCCH initiative.

Once the logo was finalised, the colour palette and core visual elements were implicitly defined and extracted from the approved design. These elements provided the foundation for the website's visual template and guided subsequent design decisions. In parallel, the project objectives, dissemination needs, and target audiences were analysed, together with a detailed review of ECHOES guidelines related to website layout, accessibility, security, and co-branding requirements. Best practices and reference examples from other European research and innovation project websites were also considered to inform the internal structure and navigation logic[6], [7], [8]. Based on this conceptual and design framework, the website was implemented using a WordPress-based content management system, selected for its flexibility, scalability, and ease of maintenance and its ease of adding and editing content without needing prior HTML knowledge. Standard web development techniques were applied to ensure responsive design, multilingual support, among other features. The website is conceived as a publicly accessible platform, available to the general public without the need for user registration. focusing on dissemination, information sharing, and stakeholder engagement rather than personalised services.

Figure 1. Approach visual workflow.

Finally, the website design and content are intended to evolve iteratively throughout the project. Updates and content population will be carried out by the partners involved in WP11 and WP12, ensuring that the website remains aligned with ongoing communication & dissemination activities. During the preparation of this deliverable, artificial intelligence tools were used exclusively to support language refinement and for the generation of temporary stock images displayed on the website. At no point was AI used to create the technical content or project-specific information presented herein

1.4. RELATION TO OTHER WORK PACKAGES, TASKS AND DELIVERABLES

D1.6 is part of WP1 “Project Coordination, Communication, and Dissemination” and serves as a central reference for the project’s visual and digital communication assets. Specifically, it supports key tasks by providing the logo and website that underpin communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement activities.

- T1.1/2.1 – Project Management and Coordination
The KINETIKA website and logo documented in D1.6 provide a shared visual and digital framework that facilitates internal coordination and external communication. By offering a coherent and recognisable identity, the deliverable helps align consortium partners’ interactions, supports reporting, and ensures that project outputs are presented consistently across all channels.
- T1.5/2.5 – Open Call Evaluation and Set-Up
D1.6 directly contributes to the Open Call (OC) tasks by providing the website infrastructure where call information, application procedures, and timelines are presented to third-party beneficiaries. The visual identity and functional design of the site ensure clarity, usability, and accessibility, enabling effective engagement with innovators participating in the “INNOVATE” and “DEMONSTRATE” calls.

Beyond WP1, the website also interfaces with technical and pilot WPs (WP3–WP5), serving as a platform to showcase pilot cases, publications, and project activities. Analytics and performance monitoring feed back into WP1, while also refining the dissemination strategy and supporting WP11/12 on Dissemination, Ecosystem Development, and Exploitation (Figure 2), including:

- T1.2/T12.2 – Communication and Ecosystem Outreach
- T1.3/T12.3 – Dissemination and Scientific Outreach
- T1.4/T12.4 – Ecosystem Development and Stakeholder Engagement

In this way, D1.6 not only documents the design and functionality of KINETIKA’s logo and website but also underpins key operational and strategic tasks, ensuring that communication, dissemination, and ecosystem-building activities are effectively implemented.

Figure 2. Relationship map of Deliverable D1.6 within the KINETIKA project.

1.5. DOCUMENT STRUCTURE

D1.6 is organised around the KINETIKA logo and the KINETIKA website; therefore, the primary sections revolve around these two elements. The deliverable is organised as follows:

- **Section 1 – Introduction**
This section provides the reader with the context and rationale behind D1.6. It outlines the purpose and scope of the document, explains the methodology and approach followed for the design and development of the KINETIKA website and logo, and clarifies the deliverable's relationship with other WPs, Ts, and outputs within the project.
- **Section 2 – Visual identity**
This section details the development of the KINETIKA logo. It explains the design choices, including the rationale behind the colour palette and graphical elements, and provides the brand guidelines to ensure consistent application across all project materials.
- **Section 3 – Project website**
This section presents a comprehensive description of the KINETIKA project website. It covers the site structure, design, and navigation, as well as its key functionalities. It also describes content management workflows, security and privacy compliance, accessibility features, and analytics monitoring. This section demonstrates how the website serves as a central tool for dissemination, stakeholder engagement, and the promotion of KINETIKA's objectives within the European CH community.

This structure (Figure 3) ensures a logical flow of information, guiding the reader from general context to specific technical, design, and operational aspects of the KINETIKA project website and logo.

Figure 3. Conceptual structure of Deliverable D1.6.

2. VISUAL IDENTITY

The visual identity of the KINETIKA project plays a key role in ensuring a coherent, recognisable and professional presence across all communication and dissemination activities from the very beginning of the project (M1). A clearly defined project logo contributes to strengthening the project's visibility[9], facilitating its identification by stakeholders and external audiences, and ensuring consistency across all project-related materials generated throughout the project lifecycle.

In the context of European collaborative research projects, the early definition of a clear and recognisable logo is essential to support effective dissemination and to ensure alignment with EC communication and visibility requirements. For this reason, the visual identity addressed in this deliverable is centred on the KINETIKA project logo, which has been conceived as the primary and unifying visual element to be used from M1 across digital and printed media, including the project website, presentations, internal and external reports and public deliverables.

Additional elements of the project's visual identity, such as extended branding materials and communication assets, will be progressively developed during the following months, building upon the logo as the core visual reference and ensuring a coherent and consistent visual framework as dissemination activities expand.

In this regard, the KINETIKA project logo serves as the central element of the project's visual identity and the primary reference for all communication and dissemination activities. It has been developed to provide a recognisable and coherent image of the project, reflecting its core essence as an initiative focused on the preservation of cultural assets with mechanical or movable parts. All guidelines and variations described in the following sections are intended to preserve the integrity, legibility and impact of the logo throughout the project lifecycle.

2.1. LOGO DESIGN AND OVERVIEW

The KINETIKA logo (Figure 4) has been developed following the guidelines of the ECCCH initiative by ECHOES, ensuring that the project is clearly recognisable as part of this broader network. In practice, this means that the logo layout includes the ECCCH logo followed by a chosen spacer element (a vertical bar), and then the KINETIKA wordmark, respecting the recommended spacing and proportions. This configuration reinforces the project's connection with ECCCH and ensures alignment with its established visual identity standards and those of sister projects.

In terms of artistic design, the logo reflects the project's essence, focused on the preservation and simulation of dynamic CH assets with mechanical or movable parts[10]. This is represented in the logotype through three distinct elements: the letter "K" of KINETIKA, rendered cleanly in the primary blue colour; a metallic plate, indicated by the primary orange colour and circular details resembling screw holes or anchors; and the pistons or keys, in primary blue for contrast against the orange plate, which convey the sense of movement central to the project's focus. The primary blue and orange tones symbolise the convergence between digital technologies (blue) and the physical nature of CH assets (orange)[11], [12]. Figure 5 provides the colour palette of the KINETIKA logo and visual identity. For certain graphic elements, a secondary purple tone derived from the combination of the primary blue and orange colours may also be used, provided it is applied consistently and only as a complementary accent to support the main colour scheme.

Figure 4. Official KINETIKA logo – horizontal configuration.

#00619E	R: 0 G: 97 B: 158	#8F727A	R: 143 G: 114 B: 122
	C: 100 M: 39 Y: 0 K: 38		C: 0 M: 20 Y: 15 K: 44
#F08129	R: 240 G: 129 B: 41	#4A4F55	R: 74 G: 79 B: 85
	C: 0 M: 46 Y: 83 K: 6		C: 13 M: 7 Y: 0 K: 67

Figure 5. KINETIKA logo colour palette.

The primary and preferred configuration of the logo is the horizontal layout. This master logo shall be used by default in all communication materials whenever space conditions allow and is always accompanied by the ECCCH logo.

To protect the visual integrity of the logo and ensure optimal visibility, its proportions and layout must always be preserved to avoid distortion or loss of recognisability. A minimum clear space has been established around the logo, preventing interference from surrounding text, images, or graphic elements and ensuring the logo remains clearly distinguishable. The minimum clear space is defined using the height of the capital letter “N” in the wordmark KINETIKA as the reference unit. No other elements may appear within this area in any application of the logo as shown in Figure 6. Using the letter “N” as a reference allows the clear space to scale proportionally with the logo size, ensuring consistency across all formats and media.

Figure 6: KINETIKA master logo with clear space defined.

Scaling is permitted only if the aspect ratio is preserved. Any form of distortion, rotation, cropping, or the application of additional graphic effects is strictly prohibited. High-resolution logo files shall always be used to guarantee clarity and a professional appearance.

If the primary horizontal logo configuration shown in Figure 4 and Figure 6 cannot be used due to space constraints, limited size, low contrast, or other practical considerations, official alternative logo variations are available to ensure consistent visual identity in all applications. These variations are described in the following section, providing approved options for vertical, simplified, or other context-specific layouts.

2.2. OFFICIAL LOGO VARIATIONS

While the primary horizontal logo configuration is the preferred option (Figure 4), specific situations may require alternative layouts to ensure legibility, recognisability, and proper integration within diverse formats and media. The following official variations have been defined to address such cases, and only the variations described in this document are authorised for use.

These variations cover both layout adaptations (vertical, and compact configurations) and colour options (greyscale and white), providing flexibility while maintaining consistency with the project's visual identity and alignment with ECCCH guidelines.

2.2.1. LAYOUT ADAPTATIONS

VERTICAL LOGO CONFIGURATION

The vertical layout (Figure 7) places the ECCCH logo above the KINETIKA wordmark, separated by the standard vertical spacer. This configuration is recommended for narrow or tall spaces where the horizontal layout would not fit, such as banners, social media profiles, or certain printed materials. It preserves all visual elements of the master logo, including the graphical symbol, the metallic plate, and the pistons or keys, maintaining the project's visual identity and recognisability.

Figure 7. KINETIKA logo – vertical configuration.

COMPACT CONFIGURATION

The compact version (Figure 8 and Figure 9) is intended for applications with very limited space, such as digital icons, small-scale prints, or situations where the full horizontal or vertical logo would compromise legibility. It may also be used to avoid redundancy when the full logo has already been displayed in a previous context. This configuration reduces the overall footprint of the logo while retaining its essential visual elements, colours, and proportions.

Figure 8. KINETIKA compact logo – horizontal configuration.

Figure 9. KINETIKA compact logo – vertical configuration.

2.2.2. COLOUR OPTIONS

GREYSCALE VERSION

The greyscale version of the logo has been developed for cases in which colour reproduction is not possible or appropriate, such as monochrome printing or specific technical limitations. This version preserves the visual hierarchy and legibility of the original design while removing chromatic information. The greyscale version of the logo in the official format (Figure 10 and Figure 11) or the compact version (Figure 12 and Figure 13) are shown below.

Figure 10. KINETIKA logo – horizontal greyscale.

Figure 11. KINETIKA logo – vertical greyscale.

Figure 12. KINETIKA compact logo – horizontal greyscale.

Figure 13. KINETIKA compact logo – vertical greyscale.

WHITE VERSION

The white version is provided for use on dark or visually complex backgrounds where sufficient contrast cannot be guaranteed with the colour or greyscale versions. The use of a blue-to-orange or orange-to-blue gradient background is strongly recommended when presenting the logo in White. The white version of the logo in the official format (Figure 14 and Figure 15) or the compact version (Figure 16 and Figure 17) are shown below.

Figure 14. KINETIKA logo – horizontal white.

Figure 15. KINETIKA logo – vertical white.

Figure 16. KINETIKA compact logo – horizontal white.

Figure 17. KINETIKA compact logo – vertical white.

2.3. LOGO APPLICATION GUIDELINES

The use of the KINETIKA logo is regulated by a set of branding guidelines aimed at ensuring coherent, consistent, and professional visual communication throughout the project's lifetime. These guidelines are mandatory for all consortium partners and for any third party involved in the production of communication or dissemination materials related to the project.

2.3.1. CORRECT USAGE PRINCIPLES

The KINETIKA logo shall always be applied in a manner that ensures maximum legibility and visual clarity. Modifying the logo colours, opacity, proportions, or orientation, or applying shadows, outlines, or any other visual effects, is strictly prohibited. If any modification is considered necessary for a specific application to enhance legibility or visibility, a formal request must be submitted to the coordinators for approval of the modified version. Furthermore, the logo shall not be placed on backgrounds that compromise its visibility or readability. Following these guidelines ensures that the KINETIKA logo remains recognisable, professional, and visually coherent across all applications, reinforcing the project's identity and its connection with the ECCCH initiative.

GENERAL PRINCIPLES

- The logo shall always be applied in a manner that ensures maximum legibility and visual clarity.
- Modification of the logo colours, opacity, proportions, orientation or cropping is strictly prohibited.
- Shadows, outlines, glows, or any other graphic effects not defined in the official variations are not permitted. If any modification is deemed necessary for a specific application to improve legibility or visibility, a formal request must be submitted to the coordinators for prior approval.
- The logo shall not be placed on backgrounds that compromise its visibility or readability. When necessary, the white or greyscale version of the logo should be used to maintain contrast.
- Minimum clear space rules, as defined in section 2.1., must always be respected.

LAYOUT AND VERSIONS

- The horizontal master logo shall be used preferably and whenever space allows.
- Alternative layouts, including vertical or compact versions, may be used in cases of limited space, reduced display size, or to avoid redundancy with previous logo appearances.
- Only official colour, greyscale, and white versions of the logo are authorised. No other colour modifications or versions may be used.

CO-BRANDING AND ECCCH ALIGNMENT

- When appearing alongside other partner logos, maintain the recommended spacing and alignment to ensure clear hierarchy and recognisability.

- The KINETIKA logo should never compete visually with other logos and must remain clearly identifiable.
- KINETIKA logo is always presented as stated in Figure 4 with the ECCCH logo.

2.3.2. ACCESS TO BRANDING DOCUMENTATION

The KINETIKA Logo Guidelines (Figure 18), including all official logo variations, colour palettes, clear space rules, and application instructions, are available to all consortium members through the official project repository and are also accessible via the official KINETIKA project website. Access to this documentation is essential to ensure that the logo is consistently applied across all project materials, both digital and printed.

Consultation of these guidelines is mandatory prior to the creation, adaptation, or production of any communication, dissemination, or promotional materials, including but not limited to presentations, reports, websites, social media content, and printed publications. This ensures that all outputs maintain a coherent visual identity, respect the minimum clear space, adhere to colour standards, and avoid any misuse or distortion of the logo.

Third parties involved in producing project-related materials, such as graphic designers, printers, or media agencies, must also follow these guidelines and obtain the official logo files from the repository or website.

Figure 18: KINETIKA's Logo Guidelines.

3. PROJECT WEBSITE

The KINETIKA project website, launched during M1 of the project, constitutes a key pillar for the dissemination and exploitation of results[13], [14]. It has been designed to be visually consistent and immediately recognisable as part of the ECCCH network, following the established ECCCH visual identity guidelines. Its main goal is to provide a centralized access point to information about the project pilots, scientific and technological developments, and outreach activities of the consortium.

<https://kinetika-eccch.eu>

Through the project's official domain, the visual identity and content are coherently integrated with the shared narrative of CH digitization. The website presented in this deliverable was initially developed as a functional and adaptable template, a white canvas, designed to evolve throughout the project's duration in response to the emerging needs of the consortium and the ECCCH ecosystem. This foundational structure allows the consortium to implement progressive updates and future integrations to ensure the website remains accessible, user-friendly, and capable of accommodating evolving project content and functionalities. In addition to its structural and functional design, the website incorporates visual assets to illustrate content in cases where project-specific materials were not yet available at the time of its initial deployment. In such instances, certain images were generated using artificial intelligence tools strictly for temporary stock purposes. These visuals will be progressively replaced with authentic project imagery as activities advance and subsequently adapted in line with the KINETIKA visual identity.

3.1. WEBSITE STRUCTURE

The back-end of the KINETIKA project website is hosted on a dedicated server using WordPress[15] as its content management system, providing a flexible, scalable, and easy-to-maintain environment. The server uses a MySQL database[16], administered through phpMyAdmin[17], which facilitates the management and control of site data. The design and structure of the WordPress site have been adapted and customized to reflect the project's visual identity, ensuring consistency with its institutional image and communication objectives. The website does not include user registration or login functionalities, as all content is publicly accessible. Administrative access is restricted exclusively to authorized project members and is managed through the standard WordPress administration panel via secure access. All form submissions and message transmissions are handled via the Simple Mail Transfer Protocol (SMTP)[18], ensuring confidentiality and protection of transmitted information. This setup guarantees high reliability, security, and ease of management, while minimizing technical complexity and potential data protection risks.

The front-end of the KINETIKA website has been structured to ensure clear and intuitive navigation, enabling visitors to access project information efficiently while maintaining consistency with the project's visual identity. The main logo, positioned prominently on all pages, serves as a link to the project's homepage, providing a familiar and immediate navigation anchor for users.

The main menu is organised into distinct sections and subsections, reflecting the key components of the project and the information needs of the consortium, stakeholders, and external audiences. Table 1 summarises the website's structure and content hierarchy.

Table 1. KINETIKA Website structure – Sections and subsections

Section	Subsection
Homepage	-
About	KINETIKA
	Cultural Heritage Cloud (ECCCH)
	Sister Projects
Pilot Cases	Overview
	Pilot 1: “Enaerios” cable system – Naxos, Greece
	Pilot 2: Cathedral bell system – Salamanca, Spain
	Pilot 3: Santa Justa elevador – Lisbon, Portugal
	Pilot 4: High Castle – Vienna, Austria
	Pilot 5: Pyhäsalmi mine – Pyhäjärvi, Finland
Media	News
	Press
	Publications
	Communication Kit
Open Calls	Overview
	OC1 - Innovate
	OC2 - Demonstrate
Contact	-

HOMEPAGE

When accessing the KINETIKA website, the user is greeted by a clean and straightforward interface that follows ECCCH standards – The KINETIKA homepage (Figure 19).

The KINETIKA homepage opens with a header featuring the project’s branded gradient from orange to blue. On the left, within the blue section, the project’s social media icons are displayed, providing direct access to its online presence. Below this header, on the default white background of the website, the KINETIKA logo is positioned on the left, while the main navigation menu, linking to the website sections presented in Table 1, is aligned to the right.

Figure 19. KINETIKA Homepage – Banner view.

At the centre of the user’s viewport, a representative image of the Bell Tower of Salamanca Cathedral is prominently featured as a banner, harmonized with the project’s primary colour palette. This banner is complemented by engaging text and the project’s slogan, “*Preserving Motion, Preserving Heritage*”, accompanied by a call-to-action button, “*Discover KINETIKA*”, linking directly to the KINETIKA project’s explanatory page. Below the main banner, after the first scroll, the homepage is divided into concise sections presenting the project’s approach, including an introductory video, key technologies, and main objectives. Content is summarized to provide visitors with a clear understanding of KINETIKA’s scope while maintaining engagement without overwhelming the user. A dedicated news area highlights the latest updates, allowing visitors to stay informed without navigating to other sections (Figure 20). Additionally, the page displays the number of consortium members and collaborating projects.

Figure 20. KINETIKA Homepage – Objectives and News view.

At the bottom of the page, a subscription form for the project’s upcoming newsletter facilitates community engagement. The footer, consistent across all website pages as the header, also includes a reference to the project’s funding by the European Union and the ECCCH identification from ECHOES,

displayed with its official logo, reinforcing the project’s alignment with the initiative. This layout is illustrated in Figure 21.

Figure 21. KINETIKA Homepage – Newsletter and footer view.

ABOUT – KINETIKA

This section of the website delves into the main technologies employed in the development of the KINETIKA project. Each technology is presented through interactive dropdown menus, allowing users to access a more detailed description of the service, including the specific technologies and methods used (Figure 22).

Figure 22. KINETIKA About>KINETIKA – KINETIKA technologies.

Following the technological overview, the section presents a comprehensive view of the consortium members, highlighting all participating entities. A dynamic map illustrates the geographical distribution of the countries involved, offering a clear visual representation of the project’s international scope. Below the map, the logos of all partner organizations are displayed, each linked to the respective

entity's official social media channels, facilitating direct engagement and providing users with access to the collaborators' broader activities within the field of digital CH.

ABOUT – CULTURAL HERITAGE CLOUD (ECCCH)

Figure 23. KINETIKA About>ECCCH.

This section of the website provides a comprehensive overview of the ECCCH, the European framework to which the KINETIKA project belongs (Figure 23). The content is presented through clear and well-structured text, highlighting the key pillars of the collaborative cloud, including its strategic objectives, main areas of action, and its role in the digital transformation of Europe's CH.

The page concludes with a direct link to the ECHOES website, the driving project behind this digital infrastructure, allowing visitors to explore in depth how collaboration and technological innovation converge to preserve and promote Europe's CH.

ABOUT – SISTER PROJECTS

This section of the website is dedicated to presenting the projects that, together with KINETIKA, form part of the ECCCH ecosystem. Given the scale and diversity of this initiative, which brings together projects pursuing the common goal of preserving cultural heritage from complementary and diverse perspectives, KINETIKA considers it essential to provide a dedicated space to showcase these sister projects. Therefore, this subsection aims to highlight the richness of approaches within the ECCCH ecosystem, illustrating how different technological, methodological, and disciplinary angles contribute collectively to the digital preservation, analysis, and valorisation of cultural heritage. By doing so, it reinforces the sense of a shared European effort while allowing each initiative to retain its distinct identity and focus.

Each project is presented through an interactive profile card that includes its identifying logo, a brief description of its main objectives, and a direct link to its official website, facilitating access to further information and encouraging exploration of the broader ECCCH project landscape (Figure 24).

Figure 24: KINETIKA About>Sister Projects.

PILOT CASES

This section of the website introduces the five Pilot Cases that constitute the initial phase of the KINETIKA project, each conceived as a real-world application of the project's technologies. The Pilot Cases area is structured through a dedicated submenu that provides access to six entries: an overview page and five individual pilot pages, one for each case study.

The Pilot Cases overview page (Figure 25) presents concise yet accurate descriptions of the five pilots, outlining their specific objectives within the overall project framework and providing context regarding their relevance, scope, and contribution to KINETIKA's goals. Digitised conceptual images of the heritage assets involved are also included, illustrating the project's technological approach and working methodology. From this overview, each pilot case can be accessed through a direct link to its dedicated page.

Figure 25. KINETIKA Pilot Cases – Overview.

Each individual pilot page (Pilot 1 to Pilot 5) is devoted to a specific case study and provides detailed, pilot-specific information. This includes a description of the cultural heritage asset, the technical challenges addressed, the technologies applied, and the expected outcomes and progress of the pilot within the project.

MEDIA - NEWS

This section of the website is dedicated to the dissemination of project-related news and events linked to the activities of the KINETIKA consortium. It is currently under development and will be implemented as a gallery-style layout, similar to the one used for the Pilot Cases section (Figure 25), to facilitate intuitive browsing and visual consistency across the website. The News section will compile updates such as project milestones, participation in conferences and workshops, public events, and other relevant dissemination actions, highlighting their direct connection with the project's progress and impact.

MEDIA - PRESS

The Press section is intended to serve as a repository of external media coverage related to the KINETIKA project. Currently under development, it will collect news items, interviews, and articles published by KINETIKA's consortium or third-party media outlets, providing direct links to the original sources to ensure visibility, transparency, and proper attribution. This section will support the monitoring of the project's external impact and media outreach.

MEDIA - PUBLICATIONS

This section will host the scientific articles, technical publications, and other research outputs generated by members of the KINETIKA consortium. It is currently under development and has been designed with flexibility in mind to accommodate future enhancements, such as integration with Zenodo or other open-access repositories. This will facilitate public access to publications, datasets, deliverables, and project results, in line with Open Science principles and EC requirements.

MEDIA - COMMUNICATION KIT

The Communication Kit section will provide a centralized repository of official dissemination materials for the KINETIKA project. It will include downloadable resources such as the project logo in its approved versions, visual identity guidelines, templates for presentations and documents, and other promotional assets. This section is currently under development and is intended to support consistent and coherent communication by consortium members and external stakeholders across all dissemination channels.

OPEN CALLS

The OCs section of the KINETIKA website is dedicated to promoting and supporting external participation in the project through two competitive calls, namely OC 1 "Innovate" and OC 2 "Demonstrate". This section serves as a centralized access point for all information related to the open call programme, providing potential applicants with a clear and structured overview of the opportunities offered by KINETIKA.

Although the OCs have not yet been launched by M2, which corresponds to the submission deadline of this deliverable, the section has already been structurally integrated into the website. Its presence anticipates future activation and ensures that the website architecture is fully prepared to host all OC-related content once the calls are officially opened. The section is designed to begin with an overview page presenting the general objectives of the open calls, their role within the overall project framework, and the types of stakeholders targeted, such as innovators, Small and Midsize Enterprises

(SMEs), research groups, and technology providers working in the field of CH. It also outlines the overall structure of the open call programme and provides direct access to the individual pages corresponding to each call.

Dedicated pages are foreseen for OC 1 “Innovate” and OC 2 “Demonstrate”, each offering comprehensive and clearly structured information tailored to the specific nature of the call. These pages describe the objectives and scope of each call, the thematic focus areas, and the expected contributions to the KINETIKA project. Emphasis will be placed on explaining how external participants can contribute either through the development of innovative concepts and technologies or through the demonstration and validation of more mature solutions in relevant operational contexts. For each OC, the website will present the full application timeline, eligibility criteria, evaluation and selection process, and implementation conditions. Clear guidance will be provided on how to apply, including submission procedures, required documentation, and access to the application platform. This approach ensures transparency, accessibility, and ease of use, supporting applicants throughout the entire process and encouraging broad participation from the cultural heritage and innovation communities.

CONTACT

This section of the website is dedicated to presenting the team responsible for the KINETIKA project and providing clear information about the individuals in charge of its coordination. Visually, the page is structured into two columns, as shown in Figure 26, to ensure clarity and ease of navigation.

In the left column, information about the project management team is presented under the heading “Project Managers”, including both the Project Managers and the Technical Manager. This section also includes a “Get in touch” area, where the official project contact email is provided together with the address of the University of Salamanca (USAL) TIDOP group’s central offices, which serve as the project’s main institutional reference point.

The right column features an intuitive contact form that allows visitors to send enquiries, comments, or suggestions directly to the KINETIKA team, ensuring straightforward and accessible communication. To complement this functionality, an interactive map based on Google Maps is integrated, enabling users to easily locate the offices and view their immediate surroundings.

Figure 26. KINETIKA Contact.

3.2. DESIGN AND VISUAL IDENTITY

The KINETIKA website has been designed to ensure visual coherence with the ECHOES-ECCCH ecosystem, making it immediately recognisable as part of the ECCCH. The design choices follow the ECCCH guidelines[5], combining the KINETIKA project's unique visual identity with the shared aesthetic of the network (Figure 27).

Figure 27. ECCCH shared website aesthetics.

At the top of each page, the header features the KINETIKA logo on the left, followed by the main horizontal navigation menu, while social media icons are positioned in the top right corner. This layout mirrors the standard navigation structure established for ECCCH projects, reinforcing visual familiarity across all project websites. Page titles are clearly displayed along with breadcrumb navigation, supported by a background image that maintains the project's colour palette and visual identity.

The website applies the primary KINETIKA colours (Figure 5) consistently across banners, buttons, and interface elements, with complementary secondary purple tones used sparingly to highlight interactive or auxiliary content. Images and graphical elements are carefully selected to harmonize with the project's identity while providing contextual relevance for CH content.

The footer, consistent across all pages, includes acknowledgements, funding information and EU disclaimer on opinions on the left (Figure 28)[4], and on the right the statement "This project is part of the Cultural Heritage Cloud initiative" with the ECHOES logo and a link to the official ECHOES website (<https://www.echoes-eccch.eu>) (Figure 29). This co-branding reinforces KINETIKA's integration within the ECCCH network and highlights the project's contribution to the European digital heritage ecosystem.

Overall, the website's design ensures that users perceive a seamless connection with the broader ECCCH network while maintaining KINETIKA's distinctive identity.

Figure 28. KINETIKA Funding information.

Figure 29. KINETIKA ECCCH footer.

3.3. FUNCTIONALITY AND FEATURES

The KINETIKA website has been developed with a focus on usability and interactivity. It integrates a variety of functionalities to ensure that visitors can easily access, navigate, and interact with the content while maintaining high standards of accessibility, security, and technical performance.

- **Responsiveness and Device Compatibility**

The website features a fully responsive design, ensuring optimal display and usability across a wide range of devices, including desktop computers, tablets (Figure 30), and mobile phones (Figure 31). All interface elements, images, and interactive components adjust seamlessly to different screen sizes and resolutions, guaranteeing a consistent user experience.

Figure 30. KINETIKA website – tablet.

Figure 31. KINETIKA website- mobile phone.

- **Interactivity and Content Navigation**

Interactive elements have been implemented throughout the website to facilitate engagement and exploration of project content. These include dropdown menus, hover effects, clickable banners, and expandable sections for detailed information. Users can navigate efficiently between project sections, pilot case studies, media content, and OC information, supported by intuitive breadcrumbs and a clear menu hierarchy.

- **Multilingual Support**

The website currently supports English and Spanish, with content dynamically selectable via the language switcher, indicated by flag icons located in the top-right corner of the page. A translation survey will be circulated among consortium partners to expand multilingual capabilities in future iterations, ensuring wider accessibility and outreach across European audiences.

- **Forms and Community Engagement Tools**

The website includes interactive forms for contacting the project team and subscribing to the KINETIKA newsletter (Figure 21). These tools support user engagement, streamline communication, and provide a channel for feedback and inquiries.

- Integration with External Repositories

Future integration with Zenodo[19] is planned to allow open access to project deliverables, datasets, and publications. This will enhance the transparency and accessibility of KINETIKA results and support the project's alignment with open science practices promoted within the ECCCH ecosystem.

3.4. CONTENT MANAGEMENT AND UPDATES

The KINETIKA website implements a structured content management approach to ensure consistency, accuracy, and timeliness of all information published. Content is centrally managed by the project's designated communication team, with oversight provided by the Project and Technical Managers to guarantee alignment with the consortium's dissemination strategy.

Content updates follow a defined workflow: contributions from partners, including news items, pilot case progress, publications, and event announcements, are submitted to the communication team, reviewed for accuracy and relevance, and then published through the content management system. High-priority items (e.g., pilot milestones, OCs, or significant news) are published as soon as they are validated. Additionally, a monthly review is conducted to assess whether new content is ready for publication, ensuring that updates occur promptly while maintaining quality control.

This structured content governance ensures that the KINETIKA website remains a reliable, up-to-date, and accessible source of information for all stakeholders, supporting both dissemination and engagement objectives throughout the project lifecycle.

3.5. SECURITY, PRIVACY, AND COMPLIANCE

The KINETIKA website adheres to robust security protocols to safeguard user data and ensure secure communications. All site traffic is routed exclusively through Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS)[20], [21], guaranteeing encrypted communication between the website and its visitors. Compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)[22], [23] is strictly ensured, with links to the privacy policy, and cookie policy provided in the footer of every page. In addition to GDPR compliance, the website uses standard cookies to enhance user experience and facilitate basic site functionality. These include session cookies[24], which maintain the user's navigation state, and performance cookies, which collect anonymous information on how visitors interact with the site to improve usability and functionality. No tracking or profiling cookies are implemented without explicit consent, and visitors are informed about the use of cookies through a visible banner (Figure 32), in line with European regulations. Users can manage their cookie preferences at any time through the provided settings.

The website also follows Search Engine Optimization (SEO) best practices[25] to maximize visibility in search engines and increase outreach to the relevant audience. Accessibility considerations have been implemented in accordance with the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.2[26], ensuring an inclusive experience for all users. In particular, the following measures have been implemented:

- All videos include subtitles, facilitating access to audiovisual content for users with hearing impairments.
- The website is fully readable at a 400% zoom level without significant loss of content or functionality, improving accessibility for users with low vision.
- All images include descriptive alternative text, allowing screen readers to correctly interpret visual information.

In addition, the implementation of new accessibility features is planned for future versions of the portal, with the aim of further enhancing the user experience and ensuring compliance with the latest digital accessibility standards.

Figure 32. KINETIKA website – cookies disclaimer.

3.6. ANALYTICS AND PERFORMANCE MONITORING

Monitoring the performance of the KINETIKA website is considered a key element for assessing the effectiveness and impact of the project's communication and dissemination activities. Website analytics provide essential insights into user engagement, content reach, and overall visibility, supporting evidence-based improvements throughout the project lifecycle.

To this end, the project foresees the incorporation of web analytics tools, such as Google Analytics [27] or equivalent GDPR-compliant solutions, to collect aggregated and anonymised information on website usage. These metrics may include page views, navigation flows, session duration, and interaction with key sections such as pilot case descriptions, news updates, and open calls. The collected data will support the identification of user trends, content performance, and usability aspects requiring optimisation. The analysis of these indicators will enable the consortium to refine dissemination strategies, adapt content to stakeholder interests, and improve the structure and accessibility of the website over time. Any future analytics implementation will be configured in full compliance with GDPR and applicable privacy regulations, ensuring transparency, user consent where required, and the protection of personal data.

BIBLIOGRAPHY AND REFERENCES

- [1] 'Advancing the Digitization and Analysis of Dynamic Cultural Heritage Objects | KINETIKA | Project | Fact Sheet | HORIZON', CORDIS | European Commission. Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101233379>
- [2] 'Echoes - Eccch - European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science', Echoes - Eccch. Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.echoes-eccch.eu/>
- [3] 'The Cultural Heritage Cloud - Research and innovation - European Commission'. Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/social-sciences-and-humanities/cultural-heritage-and-cultural-and-creative-industries-ccis/cultural-heritage-cloud_en
- [4] 'Communicating and raising EU visibility - European Commission'. Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/managing-your-project/communicating-and-raising-eu-visibility_en
- [5] wp_1031047, 'Communication Kit', Echoes - Eccch. Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.echoes-eccch.eu/communication-kit/>
- [6] 'Automata — AUTOMated enriched digitisation of Archaeological liThics and cerAMics', Automata. Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://automata-eccch.eu/>
- [7] 'CHAMELEON - A Holistic Approach to Sustainable, Digital EU Agriculture, Forestry, Livestock and Rural Development based on Reconfigurable Aerial Enablers and Edge Artificial Intelligence-on-Demand Systems'. Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://chameleon-heu.eu/>
- [8] 'Home', LAW-GAME project. Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://lawgame-project.eu/>
- [9] P. Foroudi, T. C. Melewar, and S. Gupta, 'Linking corporate logo, corporate image, and reputation: An examination of consumer perceptions in the financial setting', *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 67, no. 11, pp. 2269–2281, Nov. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2014.06.015.
- [10] B. Müller, B. Kocher, and A. Crettaz, 'The effects of visual rejuvenation through brand logos', *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 66, no. 1, pp. 82–88, Jan. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2011.07.026.
- [11] N. Hynes, 'Colour and meaning in corporate logos: An empirical study', *J Brand Manag*, vol. 16, no. 8, pp. 545–555, Jul. 2009, doi: 10.1057/bm.2008.5.
- [12] M. M. Aslam, 'Are You Selling the Right Colour? A Cross-cultural Review of Colour as a Marketing Cue', *Journal of Marketing Communications*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 15–30, Mar. 2006, doi: 10.1080/13527260500247827.
- [13] E. Ageeva, T. C. Melewar, P. Foroudi, C. Dennis, and Z. Jin, 'Examining the influence of corporate website favorability on corporate image and corporate reputation: Findings from fsQCA', *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 89, pp. 287–304, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2018.01.036.
- [14] S. J. Winter, C. Saunders, and P. Hart, 'Electronic window dressing: impression management with Websites', *European Journal of Information Systems*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 309–322, Dec. 2003, doi: 10.1057/palgrave.ejis.3000470.
- [15] 'WordPress, Your Way', WordPress.com. Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://wordpress.com/>
- [16] 'MySQL'. Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mysql.com/>
- [17] phpMyAdmin contributors, 'phpMyAdmin', phpMyAdmin. Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.phpmyadmin.net/>
- [18] 'What is the Simple Mail Transfer Protocol (SMTP)?' Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cloudflare.com/learning/email-security/what-is-smtp/>
- [19] 'Zenodo'. Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/>

- [20] 'Hypertext Transfer Protocol'. Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/chapter/monograph/abs/pii/B9780128110270000266>
- [21] 'What is HTTPS?' Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cloudflare.com/learning/ssl/what-is-https/>
- [22] D. Kloza *et al.*, 'If it ain't broke, don't fix it? Ten improvements for the upcoming tenth anniversary of the General Data Protection Regulation', *Computer Law & Security Review*, vol. 60, p. 106251, Apr. 2026, doi: 10.1016/j.clsr.2025.106251.
- [23] 'General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) – Legal Text', General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://gdpr-info.eu/>
- [24] 'Use of cookies on our websites | European Union'. Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: https://european-union.europa.eu/cookies_en
- [25] 'SEO Starter Guide: The Basics | Google Search Central | Documentation', Google for Developers. Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://developers.google.com/search/docs/fundamentals/seo-starter-guide>
- [26] W. W. A. Initiative (WAI), 'WCAG 2 Overview', Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI). Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/wcag/>
- [27] 'Google Analytics', Google for Developers. Accessed: Feb. 04, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://developers.google.com/analytics>

CONSORTIUM

CONTACT

Project Coordinator
Diego González Aguilera
daguilera@usal.es
USAL – University of Salamanca

Project Coordinator
Natalia Nuño Villanueva
Id00816629@usal.es
University of Salamanca – USAL